

Rearing yellow stem borer (YSB) for screening varietal resistance

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YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) moths lay eggs on rice plant leaves. Shortly after hatching, the neonate larvae bore into the plant tissues. Larval feeding at the vegetative and reproductive stages causes deadhearts (DH) and whiteheads.

Many cultivars are susceptible to YSB, and even moderate host plant resistance is

highly desirable. We developed a procedure to rear stem borers year-round, to help speed screening for varietal resistance.

Seedlings of IR62 (susceptible to YSB, resistant to other insect and tungro viruses) are transplanted weekly in 34- × 25- × 11-cm plastic trays (see figure). At mid-booting, a 2.5-cm-long slit is made with a scalpel in the bulging middle portion of the leaf sheath below the flag leaf. The incision is dilated to expose a small portion of the developing panicle. One to two first-instar YSB larvae are released onto the panicle and the incision closed.

At 25-30 d after infestation (DI), when larvae have pupated, plants are cut 15 cm above the base. The trays with stubbles are transferred to a 2- × 1- × 1-m screen cage for adult emergence. About 80% of the infested tillers produce moths.

Emerging moths are collected daily and transferred to oviposition cages with potted 40-d-old TN1 plants. Leaf cuts with egg masses are removed from those plants two times a week and placed in 15- × 1.5-cm test tubes or small ball jars.

At 27 ± 2 °C, eggs hatch in about a week. Emerging larvae are used for varietal screening, for basic studies, or for maintaining the insect culture. ■

Steps in rearing YSB for resistance studies.

MDU3, a new gall midge-resistant rice

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Our breeding work for gall midge (GM) *Orseolia oryzae* Wood Mason resistance identified a superior rice culture ACM8. In screenhouse and field tests in the endemic area, ACM8 yielded higher than highly susceptible IR20. ACM8 has been released as MDU3 exclusively for the GM endemic area.

MDU3 (IET6012) is a derivative of a cross involving IR8 and Warangal 1263. Grain yields in experiment station trials averaged 4.7 t/ha, 22.4% higher than IR20 (Table 1). In adaptive farmers' field trials at 24 locations, ACM8 yields averaged 4.9 t/ha, 10.9% higher than IR20. In na-

Table 1. Overall performance of MDUJ and IR20 in Tamil Nadu, India.

Trial	MDU3	IR20	Increase over IR20 (%)
<i>Grain yield (t/ha)</i>			
Research station trials ^a	4.7	3.8	22.4
Adaptive research trials ^b	4.9	4.4	10.9
AICRIP trial ^c	4.1	3.8	7.9
<i>Productivity/d (kg/ha)</i>			
	41.4	30.9	13.7

^aMean of 6 yr. ^bMean of 24 locations. ^cMean of 7 centers.

tional yield trials at seven locations throughout India, performance was encouraging. Overall performance indicates yields 13.7% higher than IR20.

MDU3 is semidwarf with high tillering ability and is nonlodging. It matures in 120-125 d, 5-10 d earlier than IR20, and has high productivity per day. The grain is long and slender with white rice; cooking quality is good.

ACM8 was screened under artificial as well as field conditions for the important pests and diseases (Table 2). It is highly resistant to GM; resistant to brown planthopper (BPH), leaffolder, and blast and moderately resistant to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) and brown leaf spot. ■

Table 2. Reaction to major insect pests and diseases at Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Pest	Score ^a	
	ACM8 (MDU3)	IR20
BPH (screenhouse)	3	7
WBPH (screenhouse)	5	7
Gall midge		
Screenhouse	0	7
Field	0	9
Leaffolder	3	7
Blast (field)		
Leaf	3	3
Neck	3	5
Brown leaf spot (field)	5	3
Sheath rot (field)	3	3

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Using rice nurseries to collect thrips for use in screening rice germplasm

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Breeding for resistance to thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) has lagged because of the lack of large pest numbers needed for screening germplasm.

Greenhouse cultures have failed to provide the thousands of thrips needed.

We developed a simple technique to collect thrips directly from rice nurseries. The nurseries are sown every 2 wk during peak thrips incidence.

Pregerminated IR64 seed was sown in 7- × 1-m beds Aug-Oct 1988 in Coimbatore. At 10, 20, and 30 d after sowing (DAS), seedlings were examined under a binocular microscope. Thrips population/seedling was 5-6 adults at 10 DAS, 60-70

nymphs at 20 DAS, and 75-80 adults at 30 DAS. Thrips nymphs were mopped up at 20 DAS by passing a wet palm 4-5 times across seedlings in the nursery and freed by dipping the hand in a pail of water (see figure). We collected 200-250 thrips per sweep.

Water containing thrips collected per 25 sweeps was poured uniformly on 7-d-old seedlings of test cultivars (including resistant Ptb 21 and susceptible TN1) grown in wooden trays (60 × 40 × 10 cm) inside a large water-filled iron tray. Each seedling was infested with 5-6 nymphs.

Alternatively, water containing thrips was poured on 30-d-old TN1 plants kept inside a water-filled tray. Nymphs settled readily on TN1 plants, which were then tapped gently over seedling trays for infestation. Using thrips collected this way, we were able to screen 400 entries for resistance. The technique can be used in areas where dry weather prevails for 3-4 mo. Thrips populations peak with the onset of dry weather; heavy rains wash them away. ■

Pest resistance—other pests

Reaction of rice cultivar Faro 11 to sugarcane cyst nematode *Heterodera sacchari*

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H. sacchari (Luc and Merny) is widespread in sugarcane cropping areas of Nigeria. In many of the mid-belt states of Nigeria, rice and sugarcane are intercropped or relay-cropped. In earlier screening of some rice varieties, all were susceptible to *H. sacchari*. We studied *H. sacchari* pathogenicity on rice.

Ten-liter plastic buckets were filled with soil collected from an *H. sacchari*-endemic field at the Nigerian Sugar Company plantation, Bacita, and planted with rice cultivar Faro 11. Inocula were juveniles emerging from cysts collected earlier from the same field using a

Schematic of procedure for collecting rice thrips from nurseries to use in screening rice germplasm for thrips resistance.